

Table S1. Primers used for PCR amplification and DNA sequencing (*: sequencing only)

Gene	Primer	Primer sequence 5'–3'	Source
18S	18S-5	CTGGTTGATYCTGCCAGT	Winnepeninckx & Backeljau 1998
	18S1100R	CTTCGAACCTCTGACTTTCG	Williams et al. 2003
	18S600F*	GGTGCCAGCAGCCGCGGT	Norén & Jondelius 1999
	18S600R*	ACCGCGGCTGCTGGCACC	Williams & Ozawa 2006
28S	D1	ACCCSCTGAA YTTAAGCAT	Colgan et al. 2003
	D3	GACGATCGATTTGCACGTCA	Vonnemann et al. 2005
	D2F*	CCCGTCTTGAAACACGGACCAAGG	Vonnemann et al. 2005
	2CR*	ACTCTCTCTTCAAAGTTCTTTTC	Dayrat et al. 2001
CAD	54F	GTNGTNTTYCARACNGGNATGGT	Moulton & Wiegmann 2004
	205R	GCNGTRTGYTCNGGRTGRAAYTG	Moulton & Wiegmann 2004
16S	H3F	ATGGCTCGTACCAAGCAGACVGC	Colgan et al. 1998
	H3R	ATATCCTTRGGCATRATRGTGAC	Colgan et al. 1998
COI	LCO1490	GGTCAACAAATCATAAAGATATTGG	Folmer et al. 1994
	HCO2198	TAAACTTCAGGGTGACCAAAAAATCA	Folmer et al. 1994